

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY
ABOUT THE SCIENTIFIC ACTIVITY OF AMIR TUMUR AND MIRZA
ULUGEBEK

Salimov Baxriddin Lutfullaevich

Associate Professor of Tashkent State Transport University

Jurayev Alisher Akbar ugli

Student of Tashkent State Transport University.

Abstract: *Understanding the personality of Amir Temur means understanding the history of Central Asia. To understand Amir Temur means to understand our identity. Ulugbek was engaged in scientific work as well as managing the political and economic life of the country. He led scientists. He worked tirelessly on himself. He developed scientific and philosophical thinking.*

Key words: *Central Asia, Amir Temur, Ulugbek, political and economic life, science.*

It is known that many works have been written about Amir Temur. Most of them are related to the authors who had conversations with Amir Temur and participated in his various campaigns. Sharafiddin Ali Yazdi's "Zafarnoma", Rui Gonzalez de Clavijo's "Dnevnik puteshestvia ko dvorsu Timura v Samarkande v 1403-1406", Ibn Arabshah's "Miracles of fate in the history of Timur", Nizamiddin Shami's "Zafarnoma" are among these works. However, there are not a few scientists who have studied the activities of Amir Temur based on historical documents. Alisher Navoi's "Majolisun Nafois" seventh meeting, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur's "Boburnoma", V.V. Bartold's works (volume 2, part 1), (Jizn Temura), G. G. Vamberi's "History of Bukhara" (volume 1), Boriboi Akhmedov's "Amir Temur" historical-bibliographic novel, academician I.M. Mominov "Amir Temur in the history of Central Asia place and role", Yevgeny Berezikov's "Temur the Great", F. Kasimov's "Bukhara during the Timurid period", "Temur and the Timurid Empire" by Abdulahad Muhammadjanov, A. Yu. "Temur" by Yakubovsky, "Dnevnik pokhoda Timura v Indiyu" by Iyasiddin Ali, "Matlai sa'dayn va majmai bahrayn" by Abdurazzokh Samarkandi, "Nashestvie Timura na Severny Kavkaz" by H. Khizriev, B. D. Grekov, A. Yu. "The Golden Horde" by Yakubovsky, "The Empire of Timura" by V. I. Zahoder, "The Truth About Amir Temur" by Ashraf Akhmedov, "The Last Days of Sahibkiran" by Turgun Fayziev, "The Grandson of Sahibkiran" by H. Davron, and hundreds of scholars whose names are not mentioned here the existence of his works is proof of our opinion. In all these works, Sahibqiran's work was not approached in the same way. These scientists, writers, state leaders tried to illuminate the activities of Amir Temur from different angles. It cannot be said that not all of the works published during the former Soviet

Union contain objective opinions. At that time, the opinions about Amir Temur were subordinated to the service of a single ideology, and events were forced to be covered from the point of view of class. Thanks to our independence, we know the exact truth about Amir Temur. Therefore, understanding the personality of Amir Temur means understanding the history of Central Asia. "To understand Amir Temur means to understand our identity" Because the history of our grandfather is more related to the history of the Uzbek people. The people's customs, lifestyle, spiritual qualities, faith also go back to the statehood of Amir Temur. "Glorifying Amir Temur means strengthening our faith in our great future, based on our roots, culture, and power, which are deeply rooted in the depths of history." Philosophical heritage left by a great man will serve our ancestors. One of such philosophical heritages is "Temur's Laws".

Muhammad Taragai-Mirza Ulugbek (1394-1449), the son of Shahrukh Mirza, who belonged to the generation of Timurids, made an incomparable contribution to the development of philosophy and science. He was interested in the science of his time from a young age. He was in the circle of scientists, poets, artists, religious scholars, scholars, took part in scientific debates and was inspired.

Ulugbek, who lived in difficult and complicated, conflicting conditions, was engaged in scientific work as well as managing the political and economic life of the country. He led scientists. He worked tirelessly on himself. He developed scientific and philosophical thinking. During his career, he wrote works dealing with philosophy, history, logic, astronomy, mathematics, natural science and law. He got acquainted with the works of Plato, Aristotle, and Ptolemy among the Greek scientists. Ulugbek made good use of the cultural heritage and philosophical views left by his ancestors, especially Central Asian scientists. In his philosophy, intelligence is not used for fighting, acquiring land, and gaining wealth, but ruling with justice, improving the country, and developing literature and science take a central place. Ulugbek was surrounded by the famous mathematician and astronomer Qazizada Rumi, who was known as the "Plato" of his time, and famous scientists Ali Kushchi, Mansur Koshi, Ali ibn Muhammad Birjandi, Miram Chalabi, Iyasiddin Jamshid, Muhammad ibn Umar Chagnini. collected the likes. Ulugbek held councils with the participation of these scientists and conducted research on the sciences of mathematics, astronomy, and geometry. Obi built an observatory on the bank of Rahmat stream. It can be seen that he did not give up his religious faith while solving the problems of nature. Materiality and spirituality were embodied in his philosophy. In 1437, Ulugbek finished the treatise "Zichi Koragoniy". His work is still not out of the hands of scientists. Working in his observatory, he determined the balance of 1018 stars. Mirzo Ulugbek, in addition to conducting scientific observations and lecturing on the science of disasters in the madrasa, also paid serious attention to cultural and household affairs. He built dozens of madrasahs, khanaqahs, mosques, and caravanserais. Bibikhanim

Mosque, Gori Amir Mausoleum, and Shahi Zinda ensemble, which had started to be built earlier, were completed. There are hundreds of works about Ulugbek, in which he is praised as a wise philosopher, a just sultan, and a teacher. Alisher Navoi's epic "Farhad and Shirin" has a special chapter called "Hymn of Ulugbek". In it, Ulugbek is described as a scientist who created heaven on earth:

My vision is a beautiful world.

The world is another sky.

Knowing this kind of knowledge is heavenly,

Andin wrote "Zichi Koragony".

Until the end of the day, my people

Writers are under his rule.

The work "Zichi Koragony" consists of a theoretical-introductory part and four large chapters. In the first chapter, the author gets acquainted with the calendars of the Chinese, Indians, Greeks, Iranians and other nations and expresses his opinion. In the second chapter, he expresses his views on practical astronomy, in the third chapter on the theory of planets, and in the fourth chapter on astrology. As a result of long years of observation and scientific investigations, Ulugbek achieves great achievements in studying the mysteries of space, defining the year, week and day. He left behind the achievements of Erostrates, Hipparchus, Ptolemy, al-Battoniy, Ibn Yunus, Nasiruddin Tusi and other astronomers who passed before him in this field.

In addition to the work "Zichi Koragony", Ulugbek also wrote the works "Treatise on determining the sine of one degree", "Risala-dar ilmu muzyka". Ulugbek's philosophy is a secular philosophy and is an important contribution to the development of world natural sciences and social sciences.

REFERENCES:

1. Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов, Севинч Акмаловна Тоғаева. ИНТЕРПРЕТАЦИЯ ПРОБЛЕМ СОЦИАЛЬНОГО СОЗНАНИЯ В ФИЛОСОФИИ. STUDYING THE PROGRESS OF SCIENCE AND ITS SHORTCOMINGS. Vol. 1 No. 2 (2024). P. 52-55.
2. Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов, Шавкатова Сарвинозхон Лазиз қизи. РАЗЛИЧНЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ ИСТОРИИ ФИЛОСОФИИ. STUDYING THE PROGRESS OF SCIENCE AND ITS SHORTCOMINGS. Vol. 1 No. 2 (2024). P. 60-63.
3. Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов, Ўралова Дилноза Орифбой қизи. РОЛЬ ФИЛОСОФИИ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ МИРОВОЗЗРЕНИЯ. STUDYING THE PROGRESS OF SCIENCE AND ITS SHORTCOMINGS. Vol. 1 No. 2 (2024). P. 56-59.
4. Салимов, Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич, Абдусатторов, Фатхулла Хайрулла Ўғли, & Ғанибоев, Дилмурод Анваржон Ўғли (2023). ТЕНГЛИК ВА БАХТ ТУШУНЧАЛАРИНИНГ ИЖТИМОЙ МУНОСАБАТЛАРДА ТУТГАН ЎРНИ. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 3 (3), 16-21.
5. Салимов, Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич, Абдухолиқов, Диёрбек Сайрбек Ўғли, & Комилов, Фарходжон Абдусамин Ўғли. (2023). ИЖТИМОЙ МУНОСАБАТЛАРНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРУВЧИ ВА ТАРТИБГА СОЛИБ ТУРУВЧИ МУҲИМ ОМИЛЛАР. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 3 (3), 41-46.
6. Салимов , Б. Л., Файзиев , С. Ф., & Қурамбаев , Ж. (2022). ЕВРОПА ОЛИМЛАРИНИНГ АСАРЛАРИДА ИНСОН ВА ИЖТИМОЙ МУНОСАБАТЛАРНИНГ ЎЗARO АЛОҚАДОРЛИГИНИНГ ТАҲЛИЛИ. Journal of Integrated Education and Research, 1(6), 44–50.